

O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY VA O'RTA MAXSUS
TA'LIM VAZIRLIGI

МИНИСТЕРСТВО ВЫСШЕГО И СРЕДНЕ-СПЕЦИАЛЬНОГО
ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН

THE MINISTRY OF HIGHER AND SECONDARY SPECIALIZED
EDUCATION OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

JIZZAX POLITEKNIKA INSTITUTI
ДЖИЗАКСКИЙ ПОЛИТЕХНИЧЕСКИЙ ИНСТИТУТ
JIZZAKH POLYTECHNIC INSTITUTE

**ISHLAB CHIQRISHNING TEXNIK,
MUHANDISLIK VA TEXNOLOGIK
MUAMMOLARINING INNOVATSION
YECHIMLARI**

**ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ РЕШЕНИЯ ТЕХНИЧЕСКИХ,
ИНЖЕНЕРНО-ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ
ЗАДАЧ ПРОИЗВОДСТВА**

**INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS TO TECHNICAL,
ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGICAL
PROBLEMS OF PRODUCTION**

**28-29
OCTOBER
2022**

Xalqaro miqyosidagi ilmiy-texnik anjuman

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Kurpayanidi Konstantin Ivanovich

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A. Usmankulov
Signature

A.Usmankulov

OLIY VA O'RTA MAXSUS TA'LIM VAZIRLIGI

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MUAMMOLARINING INNOVATSION YECHIMLARI**
mavzusidagi xalqaro miqyosidagi ilmiy-texnik anjumani materiallari to'plami

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JIZZAX-2022

Ishlab chiqarishning texnik, muhandislik va texnologik muammolarining innovatsion yechimlari Xalqaro miqyosidagi ilmiy-texnik anjuman materiallari to'plami-Jizzax: JizPI, 28-29-oktabr 2022-yil. I QISM. 1017-bet.

Xalqaro miqyosidagi ilmiy-texnik anjuman materiallarida ishlab chiqarish tarmoqlarida innovatsion texnologiyalarni joriy etishning huquqiy, iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy muammolari, sanoat, ishlab chiqarish, transport, qurilish, qishloq xo'jaligini jadal rivojlanishini ta'minlovchi energiya va resurs tejamkor texnologiyalar, texnika vositalari, mashina va uskunalarning yangi avlodi hamda materiallarni yaratish muammolari, qayta tiklanadigan energiya manbalaridan foydalanish muammolari, zamonaviy ilm-fan: dolzarb muammolar, yutuqlar va innovatsiyalar, arxitektura va qurilish sohasida kadrlarni tayyorlashning dolzarb muammolari, zamonaviy innovatsion ta'limga besh tashabbusning tatbiq etilishi, texnik oliy ta'lim muassasalarida o'qitishning pedagogik texnologiyalari sohasidagi innovatsiyalar kabi turli masalalari chuqur tahlil qilingan.

Ushbu ilmiy ma'ruza tezislari to'plamida mamlakatimizning turli yo'nalish va mutaxassislik olimlari, OTMning professor-o'qituvchilari, ilmiy tadqiqodchilar institutlari va markazlarining ilmiy xodimlari, tadqiqodchilari, magistr va talabalarining ilmiy-tadqiqot ishlari natijalari mujassamlashgan.

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Mazkur to'plamga kiritilgan ma'ruza tezislarning mazmuni, undagi statistik ma'lumotlar va me'yoriy hujjatlarning to'g'riligi hamda tanqidiy fikr-mulohazalar, keltirilgan takliflarga mualliflarning o'zlari mas'uldirlar.

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ACTIVATION OF INNOVATIVE PROCESSING AND METHODOLOGICAL DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

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The existing macroeconomic trends in the field of total informatization of the world economy, changes in the sectoral structure of production, as well as economic challenges expressed in the change of technological patterns, require a continuous revision of the basic approaches to the organization of innovation activities. One of the fundamental factors of such changes is the recently emerged phenomenon of digitalization of the economy, which is becoming increasingly important. In the context of the pandemic, the processes of digital transformation in various sectors of the economy have developed rapidly and have shown themselves to be necessary processes in the development of any branch of the economy. The main types and types of digital services such as blockchain technologies, cryptocurrencies and its processing technologies, electronic money, electronic business and others are mainly aimed at improving the quality, efficiency and reliability of information services provided based on big data such as BigData. In addition, in the digital economy, when processing big data and making decisions based on it, more attention is paid to innovative technologies using modern methods of data mining. Modern changes in the global economy determine the functioning of large-scale data flows, which become the basis for the formation and development of a digital economy capable of fully and effectively ensuring the production, processing, storage, transmission, use and protection of information. The Strategy for the Development of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, developed under the leadership of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev, defined the strategy for the transition of the republic's economy to an innovative path of development. In the context of the formation of the digital economy, innovations are playing an increasingly decisive role in the economies of developed countries. Entrepreneurial activity, highly risky and innovative in its essence, is a key aspect in the creation and diffusion of innovations. An important condition for the dynamic development of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the accelerated introduction of modern innovative and digital technologies in the economic, social and other spheres with a wide application of scientific and technological achievements. In order to accelerate the development of the country on the basis of modern achievements of world science, innovative ideas, developments and technologies, as well as the consistent implementation of the tasks defined by the Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 21, 2018 No. DP—5544 "On the approval of the strategy of innovation development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2019 — 2021" [1].

Our research has shown that in the republic there are still no effective structures of technological mediation, elements of the digital economy that promote the commercialization of the results of innovative activities that would solve many problems of innovative development of industries. There is a passivity of domestic enterprises in using the results of scientific and technical activities, which results in their low innovation activity. All this requires certain structural changes in the management of science and innovation in the context of the formation of the digital economy. Innovative activity of economic entities requires stimulation through the introduction of a flexible system of tax benefits. The importance of this instrument of state regulation is recognized in all developed countries of the world, and each country strives to find its optimal model of tax incentives for innovation activity.

At the same time, the conducted analysis showed insufficient work on the innovative development of modernization processes, diversification, increase in production volumes and expansion of the product range of competitive products in the domestic and foreign markets. In particular:

- there is still a low level of coverage of the population with higher education;

improper interaction between ministries and departments responsible for the development of scientific and innovative activities, improper coordination of the activities of research institutions and laboratories;

low level of commercialization of scientific results;

lack of highly qualified specialists in the field of innovation management, allowing to actively promote and implement technology transfer;

lack of allocated budget funds for R&D;

lack of incentive mechanisms for attracting funds from extra-budgetary and private funds;

inadequate protection of intellectual property results, lack of qualified specialists in this field;

low level of implementation of innovative technologies in the field of renewable and alternative energy sources, energy utilization of secondary resources;

the underdevelopment of corporate relations and corporate governance principles, especially in state-owned companies.

To solve the above problems, a roadmap for the innovative development of the country is needed. The Roadmap of innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan is aimed at stimulating and developing innovative activities in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In our opinion, the purpose of the Roadmap is to create conditions for innovative growth of the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan based on the concentration of knowledge and competencies in the field of scientific, scientific, technical and innovative activities in the region, the formation of advanced research, development and innovation centers, the creation of a favorable environment for the development of innovative entrepreneurship, effective innovation infrastructure of Uzbekistan [2].

Let's consider only some of the constituent elements and directions of the Roadmap:

1) human resources and human capital. Creating opportunities for identifying talented youth, building a successful career in the field of science, technology, innovation and developing the intellectual potential of Uzbekistan;

2) infrastructure and environment. Creation of conditions for research and development that correspond to modern principles of organization of scientific, scientific, technical and innovative activities and the best world practices;

3) interaction and cooperation. Formation of an effective communication system in the field of science, technology and innovation, increasing the susceptibility of the economy and society to innovation, the development of high-tech business;

4) management and investment. Promoting the formation of an effective modern management system in the field of science, technology and innovation, ensuring an increase in the investment attractiveness of research and development;

5) cooperation and integration. International scientific and technical cooperation and international integration in the field of research and technology.

CONCLUSION

In our opinion, for the effective implementation of these directions of the Roadmap in the digital economy, it is advisable to:

integrate the efforts of the state, economic sectors, large enterprises, private business, banks, scientists and university employees into innovation activities;

to form a network to promote the results of scientific and technical activities in production: technological platforms based on partnership, focusing on combining the efforts of the state, science and business in developing priorities for long-term scientific and technological development [3];

to improve the regulatory framework, as well as to intensify economic policy measures in the field of stimulating participants in innovation activities;

to carry out systemic reforms to improve the training of professional personnel for the innovative economy, focusing on the regional level of the national economy;

to form and implement major breakthrough intersectoral innovative projects;

to intensify the financing of innovative developments by enterprises, with the condition of preferential taxation, as well as attracting banking and private investments;

to form a competitive national market that stimulates the transition of the economy to an innovative path of development and the effective use of limited economic resources;

simplify the scheme and requirements for obtaining bank package loans to actively stimulate the development of innovative enterprises, especially in the regions;

to develop an adequate model of tax incentives for attracting innovative technologies to the development of national business entities;

create centers for the collective use of unique scientific and technical equipment using the achievements of the digital economy;

based on the use of the results of the assessment of the effectiveness of the business environment, international ratings to activate production with high competitiveness and export of high-tech and digital products;

to develop the geography of international cooperation in the field of development of innovative technologies.

References:

1. *On the approval of the strategy of innovative development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2019 — 2021. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. DP-5544 of September 21, 2018, // National Database of Legislation, 22.09.2018, No. 06/18/5544/1951.*

2. Kurpayanidi, K. (2021). National innovation system as a key factor in the sustainable development of the economy of Uzbekistan. E3S Web of Conferences, Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202125805026>

3. Sehnem, S., de Queiroz, A. A. F. S., Pereira, S. C. F., dos Santos Correia, G., & Kuzma, E. (2022). Circular economy and innovation: A look from the perspective of organizational capabilities. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 31(1), 236-250.

МАҲСУЛОТНИ БЕНУҚСОН ТАЙЁРЛАШ ТИЗИМИ

Жиззах Политехника Институтини Ассистенти. Қосимов О.Ф.

Маҳсулотни бенуқсон тайёрлаш (МБТ) ва уни ТТБ га ёки буюртмачига биринчи тақдимдаёқ топшириш Саратов тизими Саратов самолетсозлик заводида 1955 йилда ишлаб чиқилди ва жорий этилди. Бу тизим заводда Б.А. Дубовиковнинг бевосита иштирокида яратилди.

Ҳисобот вақти смена, ҳафта, ой ичида маҳсулотни биринчи тақдимдаёқ топшириш фоизи билан тавсифланадиган меҳнат сифатини баҳолаш тизими асосида сифат кўрсаткичи қуйидагича аниқланади:

$$(1) \quad K = \frac{P_T}{N_T} \cdot 100\%,$$

бунда P_T – T вақт ичида биринчи тақдимдаёқ ТТБ қабул қилган маҳсулот миқдори;

N_T – T вақт ичида ТТБ га тақдим этилган маҳсулот миқдори.

Бунда алоҳида ишчи, бригада, участка, цехнинг меҳнат сифати баҳоланган, баҳо натижаси бўйича мукофот миқдори аниқланган.

Саратов тизимини Ўзбекистоннинг 24 халқ хўжалиги тармоқлари қўллаган. Айниқса, бу тизим электротехника, электрон ва енгил саноат корхоналарида самарали ишлади. Масалан, Тошкент радиодеталлар заводида биринчи тақдимдаёқ буюмларнинг 99,5 фоизи, “Тошкенкабель”, электрон техника, “Қизил Тонг” тикувчилик фирмасида, Олмалик мебель фабрикасида – 95 фоизи ТТБ га

ОБ ОДНОЙ ФУНКЦИИ КАРЛЕМАНА ДЛЯ БИГАРМОНИЧЕСКИХ ФУНКЦИЙ ЗАДАННОЙ В ДВУМЕРНОМ ЕВКЛИДОВОМ ПРОСТРАНСТВЕ З.Р. Ашурова [ОБ]	145
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